

A study of practicing degree of schools principals in dealing with students positive behaviors

Bassam Mahmoud Bany Yassien¹, Najwa Abedalhameed Draawsheh²

¹Department of Educational Science, Irbid College university, Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan

²Department of Educational Science, Jadara University, Jordan

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ABSTRACT

The importance of the study is to find out the relationship of how school principals dealing with positive behavior of students in Irbid first educational Directorate, in order to shed light On these practice to promote students positive behavior. The study aimed to identify the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their administrative and technical tasks and its relationship with the positive behaviors of students, from teachers' standpoint. Study sample consist of 310 male and female teachers who were selected through the simple random method from the 1022 study population members, and to achieve the study objectives, researcher developed a questionnaire as the study tool and was checked to ensure its sincerity and reliability. The study results showed that the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their administrative and technical tasks, from the teachers' standpoint came to a medium degree, while there weren't any statistically significant differences according to the qualification and experience variables. The results showed that practice degree of secondary school students toward the positive behavior, from teachers' standpoint came to a medium degree, and also showed a statistically significance correlation at level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between student's behavior toward school and colleagues, and the positive attitude of students as a whole and the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks.

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Corresponding Author:

Bassam Mahmoud Bany Yasseien
Department of Educational Science
Irbid College University
Irbid P.O.Box,1293, Jordan
E-mail: Bassam_b_y@yahoo.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Education consider primarily responsible for the development of human societies and it formulate their intellectual and scientific foundation, and has a prominent role in the development of national affiliation and the preparation of various human resources at its different levels. In addition, it's a tool for society's development and advancement by utilizing their available energies and investing it in the desire direction, as far as possible, where management take high position in the educational institutions as being concerned with all the factors that influence the learning and teaching process, and the administrative practices effect all these factors which make the management one of the most important success factors to achieve the objectives that pursued by those institutions [1].

Principals occupy an important position in the school program in general, as leaders of the school where many successes depend on their leaderships and everyone ask guidance from them, all teachers,

students, and parents turn to them at one situation or another for guidance. Principals are responsible for planning to serve the school community, and therefore they have to put an active program to serve the local environment, help to coordinate the social, health, and recreational services in the local school community, put the plans for public relation programs, meet parents and other visitors and discuss the school problems with them, and declare the school objectives and its policy, and explain methods used to achieve them [2]. Hussaib [3] showed that principals are responsible for the educational process at their school, implement the regulations, laws, and curricula, provide all circumstances and capabilities that help to guide student's growth mentally, physically, psychologically, spiritually, and socially, improve the educational process to achieve this growth, organize teamwork at the school, and supervise and execute the different administrative tasks and issues to create a suitable educational environment and achieve the desired goals.

Students consider an essential element in the educational institution, and their stability is an important path in the right direction, and in order for students to arrive to the desire level in the educational and behavioral aspect they must be honest and trustworthy in dealing with their colleagues and teachers, and also they must respect working as a team and provide advice and guidance to their classmates [4]. An increase of individuals' efficiency at different functional positions require from them positive thinking practices to be more able to adapt to events and situations, overcome difficulties, change the behavior of individuals who work under their responsibilities to desired behaviors, and discard dangerous and undesirable behaviors .

Many studies have been conducted on the positive behavior support programs and its effectiveness at the school level, such as the study of Steven, [5], about the behavioral plans at schools that implement the positive behavior support programs and the schools that do not implement it, and the study of Diab, [6], which dealt with the design of technical support systems for students with special needs through building a comprehensive culture in school by using the positive behavior support approach. This positive behavior support approach also used to organize the classes and lessons at school to protect it from the behavioral problems [7].

This study came to identify the practicing degree of secondary school principals in dealing with the positive behaviors of students, from teachers' standpoint at Irbid First Educational Directorate, by answering the following questions:

- a. What is the practicing degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks, from the teachers' standpoint?
- b. What is the practicing degree of secondary school students toward positive behavior, from teachers' standpoint?
- c. Is there any statistical significance correlation at level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks and the practice degree of positive behaviors among students, from teachers' standpoint?

This study aimed to identify the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their administrative and technical tasks and its relationship with the positive behaviors of students, from the teachers' standpoint through achieving the following goals:

- a. To identify the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks, from teachers' standpoint in order to highlight these practices, improve the modest practice degrees, and strengthen the positive practices.
- b. To identify the practice degree of secondary school students toward their positive behaviors, from teachers' standpoint in order to pay attention to the positive behaviors, promote it, and focus on improving the practices that the study will reveal its low degree.
- c. To identify the correlation between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks and practice degree of positive behaviors among students, from teachers' standpoint, in order to make the recommendations that indicate this relationship, and the need to improve students' behaviors through high performance tasks by school administrators or principals.

The study importance comes from its search for the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their tasks, which may be related to the positive behaviors of students with hope for the following to benefit from this study results:

- a. Education officials in the Ministry of education, where the study results provide them with feedback on the role of secondary school principals to promote the positive behaviors among students.
- b. High school principals and teachers, where the study results provide them with students practice degree of positive behaviors.
- c. Parents, where the study results offer them feedback about their children positive behaviors at high schools.
- d. Social and cultural institutions, where the study results provide them with information about students' behaviors.

- e. Educational researchers, where the study results assist them in the area of management practices of school principals and the positive behaviors of students.

The definitions of following terms were used in the study; 1) School principal: the head official of school, who is responsible for nurturing the students, taking care of them, giving them the full opportunity for development, organizing the workflow at school, and serving environment around the school, where the ethical situation and cultural level of school depend on the trends and personalities of principal, and their awareness of the mission they are out to execute [8]; 2) Tasks: functions, jobs, and duties related to changing the behaviors of educational process associates, such as teachers and pupils in order to achieve the objectives of the school [9]; 3) Positive behaviors: the conducts, manners, and habits that result from the positive thinking of individuals through full investment for human resources, capabilities, and potentials. Researchers identify the practices degree of positive behaviors procedurally: the degree recorded by respondents on the study tool to measure the practice degree of positive behaviors among high school students at Irbid basic education, from the teachers' standpoint.

Study results were restricted to the following: 1) Subject boundaries: the study topic was restricted to the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their administrative and technical tasks and its relationship with the positive behaviors of students, from teachers' standpoint; 2) Human boundaries: the human boundaries were restricted to a sample of secondary school teachers at Irbid First Educational Directorate, for the second term of (2018-2019) academic year; 3) Study limitations: The generalization of study results depend on the psychometric properties of its tools, and on similar population. The present study used the description design, to suite it for the purposes of the present study. To achieve the objectives of the study, it determined the study problems, questions and objectives. Checklist prepared and data collected and results analyzed.

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

This part will display the previous studies related to the study topic, and were displayed and arranged chronologically from the newest to the oldest as follows:

The aim of a study by David [10] is to find out the relationship between principal behavior on students, teacher and school outcomes. The researcher reviewed the empirical literature from 42 studies of principal behaviors and student, teacher and school outcomes and conduct a meta-analysis of these relationships. The findings: 1) we find direct evidence of the relationship between principal behaviors and student achievement (0.09-0.17 standard deviations), teacher well-being (0.34 *SD*), teacher instructional practices (0.34 *SD*), and school organizational health (0.69 *SD*); 2) we find that prior literature may overstate the unique importance of instructional management as a tool to improve student achievement outcomes; and 3) the preceding findings are based almost entirely on observational studies because the causal evidence base on school leadership behaviors is non-existent.

The aim of a study by Charles [11] is to find out the relationship between principals' leadership qualities and their administrative tasks performance effectiveness as perceived by secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 820 teacher from 82 secondary schools. The finding showed that there was a significant positive correlation between principals' leadership qualities and their administrative tasks performance effectiveness. Premised on the findings of this study, it was concluded that leadership qualities are strong determinants of principals' administrative task performance effectiveness in secondary schools.

The study by Naji [12] aimed to recognize the practice degree of administrative and technical skills among the public education school principals of Najran and its availability degree, and would it change according to the sex, qualifications, and years of experience variables. The study sample consist of (87) male and female principals with a percentage of (45.3%) from the overall (192) original study population, and the study used the descriptive analytical approach. Study results indicate that practice degree of administrative and technical skills among the public education school principals in general came to a medium degree. Results also showed no differences due to the years of experience variable, while found differences due to the sex variable at the organizing aspect, and in favor of males, and for the qualification variable in the areas of organizing and financial affairs, and in favor of undergraduate degree holders and above.

While Fahd [13], conducted a study that aimed to identify the relationship between the practice level of secondary school principals toward their management and leadership roles and the level of human relations, from the teachers' standpoint at State of Kuwait. Study sample consist of (354) teachers who were selected by the random method, and use the questionnaire as a study tool. Study results showed that practice level of secondary school principals toward their management and leadership roles was high and the level of human relations was medium. Results also indicate statistically insignificant differences in the practice level of management and leadership roles, due to the qualification, experience, and sex variables.

But Hassan [14] study aimed to identify the practice degree of school principals toward the supervisory tasks, where the study sample consist of (200) male and female teachers. The questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data, and also developed a tool to measure the supervisory tasks of principals in Jordan, which consisted of four areas that contain (36) items. The major results of the study show that order of aspects according to the arithmetic means were as follow: development of human relations, planning, and professional growth of teachers. Results also showed that practice degree of school principals was medium, statistically insignificant differences for the sex variable, and statistically significant differences for both of experience and qualification, and the interaction of sex and experience and also sex and experience and qualification.

Al-Zahrani study [15] aimed to reveal the role of high school principals and teachers at Taif municipality toward the required tasks from them to face the behavioral problems among students, from the standpoint of students themselves. The study sample consist of (400) male and female students from the literary and scientific branches, at the eastern area of Taif in KSA during first semester of the academic year (2010-2011). The study results showed that role of school principals to address the behavioral problems of students, from their perspective came to a medium degree, and showed that role of teachers to deal with the behavioral problems of students, from their perspective was also medium. Results indicate a statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) toward the role of high school principals and teachers to address the behavioral problems, due to the differences in sex variable categories and in favor of females, and also indicate a statistically significant differences at level ($\alpha = 0.05$) toward the role of major principals, where the differences came in favor of the literary branch due to the experience and qualification variables.

Al-Amarat [16] conducted a study that aimed to identify the performance degree of school principals at Petra Education Directorate, from the standpoint of teachers. Study used the questionnaire as a tool and the study sample consist of (236) male and female teachers at the public school of Petra Education Directorate. The study results showed that performance degree of school principals' effectiveness, from the standpoint of teachers came high, and showed statistically significant differences due to the experience and qualification variables.

But, Stavriindies [17] performed a study that aimed to identify the violence circulation average among the secondary school students in Cyprus, as one of the leading behavioral problems that face the Cyprus high schools, where a scale of violence was build and implemented on (1645) students. Study results confirmed that (17%) of students are practicing violent behaviors, and confirmed that existence of indicative programs may contribute significantly to reduce the level of violence among these students.

Barakat [18] did a study that aimed to identify the indications of negative classroom behavior among basic level students, from the standpoint of teachers and identify the techniques used by those teachers to face the behavioral signs. Study sample consist of (832) male and female teachers, (413) are males and (419) are females, and the study used questionnaire for data collection. Study results showed that level of teachers' evaluation toward the indications of negative classroom behavior among basic level students was medium, and their level of facing these behaviors were generally high.

The study of Al-Momani [19] dealt with the effective methods that connect secondary school principals with their students at Ajloun Governate, Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan from the standpoint of principals, teachers, students, and parents. To achieve this purpose a sample was chosen randomly which consist of (24) principals, (169) teachers, (523) students, and (126) parents from the various areas of Ajloun. Study results demonstrated that effective methods which connect secondary school principals with their students at Ajloun Governate was medium, but in regard to the responses evaluation of teachers, students, and parents sample toward the effective methods that connect secondary school principals with their students at Ajloun Governate were at low degree. Study also found a statistically significant difference at level ($\alpha \geq 0.01$) toward the effective methods that connect principals with their students in the secondary schools of Ajloun, due to the sex variable in principals' perceptions and the differences were in favor of females. In addition, it showed no differences in teachers' perceptions toward the sex variable, but there are differences in students' perceptions toward the sex variable and in favor of female students.

Lawrence [20] study aimed to identify some behavioral disorders among the high school students in Swaziland, where the study sample consist of (300) high school students, and the questionnaire was used to collect data. Study results showed that aggressive behavior is the most common behavioral disorders that could face the high school students. Study results confirmed that reinforcement method consider one of the most effective methods to reduce the behavioral problems among high school students in Swaziland.

Finally, a study Abu-Shareaha, Zidan [21], aims to know the degree of schools principals practicing innovation and its relationship with the teachers' professional development; the sample of the study is consisted 415 teachers; the sample of the study is consisted of 205 male and female teachers from members of the study population. The results of the study showed as well that the degree of schools teachers' professional development was great according to the teachers' point of view. The result of the study showed a

positive correlation of statistical significance at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among the averages of schools teachers estimations in the domains of schools principals practicing innovation and their estimations of the teachers professional development

The present study distinguished from the others in the population of the study, and the sample used, as it is the first study that take place in Irbid first Educational Directorate/Jordan, and this indicates that the field's have lack of such study.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The present study used the description design, to suite it for the purposes of the present study. To achieve the objectives of the study, it determined the study problems, questions and objectives. Checklist prepared and data collected and results analyzed. Study results were restricted to the following:

- a. **Subject Boundaries:** the study topic was restricted to the practice degree of secondary school principals at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their administrative and technical tasks and its relationship with the positive behaviors of students, from teachers' standpoint.
- b. **Human Boundaries:** the human boundaries were restricted to a sample of secondary school teachers at Irbid First Educational Directorate , for the second term of (2018-2019) academic year.
- c. **Study Limitations:** The generalization of study results depend on the psychometric properties of its tools, and on similar population.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. First question results, which indicate:

What is the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks, at Irbid First Educational Directorate from the teachers' standpoint?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the study sample members' responses on the aspects of secondary school principals' practice degree toward their administrative and technical tasks, from the standpoint of teachers as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the practice degree of school principal toward their administrative and technical tasks

Number	Aspect	Mean	STDEV	Degree
1	Administrative tasks	2.886	0.6544	Medium
2	Technical tasks	2.846	0.5658	Medium
Principals' practice degree toward their administrative and technical tasks		2.865	0.6013	Medium

It notice from Table 1, that administrative tasks received the highest response with an arithmetic mean of (2.886) and a standard deviation of (0.6544), which indicates a medium degree of administrative tasks level, while the technical tasks got an arithmetic mean of (2.846) and a standard deviation of (0.6013), and also got a medium degree. In addition, the average response to study sample members on the practice degree of school principals toward the administrative and technical tasks got an arithmetic mean of (2.865) with medium degree.

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the administrative and technical tasks, as follow:

a. First: administrative tasks

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of study sample members on the administrative tasks items, as illustrated in Table 2. It notice from Table 2, that arithmetic means of study aspects were all at medium degree, where the item "Organize classroom visits for teachers" on the highest response with an arithmetic mean of (3.13), and a standard deviation of (1.133), followed by the item "Involve teachers at school in the plans development process" with an arithmetic mean of (3.07), and a standard deviation of (.833), at medium degree, and the item "Manage the teachers' committee meetings efficiently" ranked second to last with an arithmetic mean of (2.74) and a standard deviation of (.734), at medium degree, but at the last rank came the item "Prepare different activities to serve the school curricula" with an arithmetic mean of (2.73), and a standard deviation of (.739), and also at medium degree.

Table 2. Means and standard deviations for the responses of study sample members on administrative tasks items, in descending order

Number	Rank	Item	Mean	STDEV	Practice Degree
1	1	Organize Classroom Visits for teachers	3.13	1.133	Medium
2	2	Involve teachers at School in the plans development process	3.07	0.833	Medium
3	3	Follow the teaching and learning process continuously	3.04	1.010	Medium
4	4	Engage students in formulating the school plans	2.97	0.962	Medium
5	5	Delegate tasks to teachers according to their competencies and capabilities	2.91	0.762	Medium
6	6	Ensure local community participation to formulate school plans	2.90	0.761	Medium
7	6	Coordinate efforts with supervisors to raise teacher's efficiency	2.90	0.761	Medium
8	7	Collects data related to students accurately	2.88	0.846	Medium
9	7	Evaluate teacher's performance fairly and objectively	2.88	0.825	Medium
10	8	Build new & good relationships with students	2.87	0.813	Medium
11	9	Evaluate the school performance of teachers continuously	2.86	0.751	Medium
12	10	Offer innovative solutions for problems at the school	2.84	0.826	Medium
13	11	Develop an annual plan for school activities	2.83	1.209	Medium
14	12	Analyze the school curricula	2.82	0.757	Medium
15	13	Hold regular meetings for parents committee	2.80	0.759	Medium
16	14	Cooperate with parents in regard to their children.	2.79	0.758	Medium
17	15	Manage the teachers' committee meetings efficiently	2.74	0.734	Medium
18	16	Prepare different activities to serve the school curricula	2.73	0.739	Medium
Administrative Tasks			2.886	0.6544	Medium

b. Second: technical tasks

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of study sample members on the technical tasks items, as illustrates through Table 3. It notice from Table 3, that arithmetic means of study aspects were all at medium degree, where the item " Prepare the required plans for school work" got the highest response with an arithmetic mean of (3.13), and a standard deviation of (1.127), followed by item "Explore teachers' needs and their professional development" with an arithmetic mean of (3.05), and a standard deviation of (.829) at medium degree, and the item "Helps teachers to perform their duties and tasks" ranked second to last with an arithmetic mean of (2.66), and a standard deviation of (.802), at medium degree, but at last rank came the item "Find practical solutions for the problems that face teachers in school" with an arithmetic mean of (2.64), and a standard deviation of (.791), and also at medium degree.

Table 3. Means and standard deviations for the responses of study sample members on technical tasks items, in descending order

Number	Rank	Item	Mean	STDEV	Practice Degree
1	1	Prepare the required plans for school work	3.13	1.127	Medium
2	2	Explore teachers' needs and their professional development	3.05	0.829	Medium
3	3	Use teamwork method to achieve the educational goals	3.04	0.991	Medium
4	4	Provide comfortable working environment for all teachers	2.92	0.764	Medium
5	5	Participate with teachers at the local community social events	2.91	0.923	Medium
6	5	Build new & good relationships with teachers	2.91	0.851	Medium
7	6	Lead meetings with teachers as needed	2.87	0.828	Medium
8	7	Engage students in identifying their educational needs in cooperation with them	2.85	1.212	Medium
9	7	Provides everything needed for the learning & teaching process	2.85	1.314	Medium
10	8	Follow up on school committees	2.83	0.772	Medium
11	9	Organize social visits for teachers outside the school	2.82	0.804	Medium
12	10	Fosters the cooperation between teachers at school	2.82	0.769	Medium
13	11	Hold teacher training courses inside the school	2.80	0.759	Medium
14	12	Coordinate efforts between teachers and education supervisors	2.78	0.777	Medium
15	12	Specify with teachers their educational needs to implement the school plans	2.78	1.079	Medium
16	13	Discuss with concerned authorities the curricula effectiveness	2.76	0.736	Medium
17	14	Distribute school budget orderly on all educational needs	2.75	1.067	Medium
18	15	Care about activating parents committee to solve the student problems	2.74	0.736	Medium
19	16	Helps teachers to perform their duties and tasks	2.66	0.802	Medium
20	17	Find practical solutions for the problems that face teachers in school	2.64	0.791	Medium
Technical Tasks			2.846	0.5658	Medium

4.1.1. Discuss the results of first question, which entitle:

What is the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks, at Irbid First Educational Directorate from the teachers' standpoint?

The results of first question indicate that practice degree of secondary school principals toward their tasks came at medium degree on the overall degree of all items of this aspect, where came first the items that talk about planning at medium degree and this aspect is often theoretical and planning might be a result of yearly accumulations, which means that principal does not make a great effort in the planning process, and it is weakness that showed clearly in other items which didn't rise up to the required level of work assigned to the principal. A principal who does not involve students or teachers in specifying their educational needs or in making school plans, and does not distribute school budget in a way that meet school needs and does that at medium degree. A principal who does not provide a comfortable working environment, does not care much for communicating with teachers, local community, or parents, does not use teamwork method to achieve the educational goals, does not follow up on the learning process, does not care about finding practical solutions to the problems that face the school staff, and do not appear in the school the atmosphere of collaboration and the professional development of employees.

This result may indicate that principals do not perform their duties properly, do not collect data about students accurately, lack of dealing with students with humanity, do not delegate tasks on teachers based on their competencies, and do not care about following the work of school committees, but instead there is a clear failure in all administrative and technical tasks of school principals, which reflected badly on all inputs and outputs of education process, not achieving the planned educational objectives, and the threat of arriving to undesirable results in the educational system.

This result may also due to lack of control and supervision by the Ministry of Education on the school principals, which encourage them to abandon their responsibilities or be short due to their knowledge that results won't be followed by the senior management, lack of coordination between teachers and supervisors efforts, failure to provide all necessary things for the educational and teaching process by the Ministry of Education, and failure to adopt the programs needed to follow all aspects of students' educational growth. This result may be attributed to the functional accretions and burdens of high school principals, in conjunction with the lack of confidence in their work team, which push them to stop doing their tasks and duties at the best possible way, and failure to involve the teachers in the planning, implementation, and evaluation processes, which increases their workload and undermine their capabilities to follow things quite effectively.

The result may also be explained through the weakness of high schools administrative staffs and the failure to recruit them professionally enough, which make them less endurance with workload and its requirements. This result agreed with the study results of Ibdah and Jaradat at low degree, and the study of Al-Taani, but it disagree with Al-Amarat study where it came at high degree, Alomari study with also high degree, and Belpeacy [22].

4.2. Second question results, which indicate:

What is the practice degree of secondary school students toward positive behavior, at Irbid First Educational Directorate from teachers' standpoint?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the study sample members' responses on the aspects of secondary school students' practice degree toward positive behavior, at Irbid First Educational Directorate from the standpoint of teachers as illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4. Means and STDEV of secondary schools male and female teachers' responses on the questionnaire aspects, at Irbid basic education

Number	Aspect	Mean	STDEV	Rank	Practice Degree
1	Student behaviors toward school	2.87	0.679	1	Medium
2	Student behaviors toward classmates	2.72	0.620	2	Medium
	Questionnaire overall degree	2.79	0.635		Medium

It notice from Table 4, that first aspect "Student behaviors toward school" received the highest response with an arithmetic mean of (2.87), and a standard deviation of (0.679), which indicate a medium degree of positive behaviors, while the second aspect "Student behaviors toward classmates" got the second rank with an arithmetic mean of (2.72), and a standard deviation of (0.620), and also got a medium degree. In addition, the average response of study sample members on the questionnaire as a whole refer to an arithmetic mean of (2.79) and a standard deviation of (0.635), at a medium degree.

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were also calculated for the items of positive behaviors' aspects, from the standpoint of male and female teachers as illustrated in Tables 5 and Table 6.

4.3. First aspect: Student behaviors toward school

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of study sample members on the first aspect "Student behaviors toward school" items, as illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the responses of study sample members on the first aspect "student behaviors toward school" items, in descending order

Number	Rank	Item	Mean	STDEV	Practice Degree
1	4	Take care of school environment	2.94	0.967	Medium
2	1	Maintain the cleanliness of school	2.92	0.771	Medium
3	3	Commit to the proper school uniform	2.91	0.762	Medium
4	6	Commit to the preparation of daily lessons	2.91	0.762	Medium
5	2	Come to school early	2.90	0.759	Medium
6	7	Take permission to get out of class when necessary	2.89	0.772	Medium
7	8	Respect teachers at the school	2.86	0.797	Medium
8	5	Adhere to the instructions of discipline and order	2.85	1.065	Medium
9	10	Discipline appropriately inside the classroom	2.83	0.781	Medium
10	11	Commit to the right healthy habits at school	2.80	0.759	Medium
11	9	Complete homework on time	2.78	0.752	Medium
Student behaviors toward school			2.87	0.679	Medium

It notice from Table 5, that arithmetic means for the items of study aspect were all at medium degree, where the item "Take care of school environment" got the first rank with the highest arithmetic mean of (2.94) and a standard deviation of (0.967), at a medium degree, followed by the item "Maintain the cleanliness of school" at second place with an arithmetic mean of (2.92), and a standard deviation of (.771), at medium degree, and the item "Commit to the right healthy habits at school" ranked second to last with an arithmetic mean of (2.80), and a standard deviation of (.759), at medium degree, but at the last rank came the item "Complete homework on time" with an arithmetic mean of (2.78) and a standard deviation of (.752), and also at medium degree.

4.4. Second aspect: Student behaviors toward classmates

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of study sample members on the second aspect "Student behaviors toward classmates" items, as illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the responses of study sample members on the second aspect "student behaviors toward classmates" items, in descending order

Number	Rank	Item	Mean	STDEV	Practice Degree
1	5	Participate with classmates in cleanliness campaigns at society	2.88	0.825	Medium
2	3	Reject the aggressive behavior with others	2.87	0.824	Medium
3	4	Accept opinions of other people	2.85	0.759	Medium
4	7	Commit to the social values	2.84	0.760	Medium
5	6	Criticize classmates in style and in a proper way	2.83	0.811	Medium
6	8	The actions of student described as trustworthy	2.82	0.769	Medium
7	2	Deal respectfully with classmates	2.72	0.753	Medium
8	1	Assist classmates in the school activities	2.70	0.742	Medium
9	9	Care about personal cleanness	2.62	0.791	Medium
10	10	Keep away from cheating during exams	2.61	0.796	Medium
11	12	Hold on to the honesty values	2.46	0.889	Medium
12	11	Offer opinion with respect	2.42	0.707	Medium
Student behaviors toward classmates			2.72	0.620	Medium

It notice from Table 6, that arithmetic means for the items of study aspect were all at medium degree, where the item "Participate with classmates in cleanliness campaigns at society" got the first rank with the highest arithmetic mean of (2.88), and a standard deviation of (0.825), at a medium degree, followed by the item "Reject the aggressive behavior with others" at second place with an arithmetic mean of (2.87), and a standard deviation of (.824) at medium degree, and the item "Hold on to the honesty values" ranked second to last with an arithmetic mean of (2.46), and a standard deviation of (.889), at medium degree, but at the last rank came the item "Offer opinion with respect" with an arithmetic mean of (2.42), and a standard deviation of (.707), and also at medium degree.

4.5. Discuss the results of second question, which entitle:

What is the practice degree of secondary school students toward positive behavior, at Irbid First Educational Directorate from the teachers' standpoint?

The results of second question indicate that practice degree of secondary school principals, at Irbid First Educational Directorate toward their positive behaviors came at medium degree, both toward their school or toward their classmates which indicate that student behavior in maintaining the cleanliness of school is unsatisfactory to raise to the required degree, where coming to school early is unsatisfactory, committing to school uniforms is unsatisfactory, as well as maintaining the school environment is unsatisfactory. Student does not care much about the respect of teachers or the instructions of discipline and order, the discipline in the classroom is unsatisfactory, hardly ever adhere to prepare daily lessons, or doing homework on time. Demonstrating the positive behavior towards his classmates unsatisfactory, rarely participate with the classmates in society cleanliness campaigns and does not always help classmates in the school activities, rarely reject the aggressive behavior with others, and rarely accept the opinions of others. In addition, the commitment to social values is unsatisfactory where student criticize their classmates inappropriately, rarely student actions can be describe with honesty and integrity, and rarely give opinion with respect.

This result may be due to the nature of growth stage for the secondary students, their attempt to rebel against the societal values system, and prove themselves, where students think that through these inappropriate behaviors will attract the attention of others and get the admiration of classmates. This may be a result of the weak relationship between the student and school, where school does not provide enough extracurricular activities to work on absorbing and investing the energies of students, but care more about finishing the educational curricula, which generate weariness of students and lead them to turn it into negative behaviors, and this issue rest primarily on management as the concern party of student growth; in all its aspects, therefore management has to provide students with the educational activities that help their growth, support the mutual relationship between them and school, and work to change their behaviors for the best.

This result can be explain on the basis of student's community education nature, which may support the roughness when dealing with others, disrespect the opinions of others, and the attempt to control others unjustly. This result agreed with the study results of Barakat, which showed that evaluation level of teachers toward the indications of classroom negative behavior among the basic school students was medium, and their facing level of these behaviors were generally high, while it disagree with the study results of Lawrence, which showed that aggressive behavior is the most common behavioral disorders that may face the high school students. The study results confirmed that method of reinforcement consider one of the most effective methods to reduce the behavioral problems among high school students in Swaziland.

4.6. Third question results, which indicate:

Is there any statistical significance correlation at level ($\alpha = 0.05$), between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks and the practice degree of positive behaviors among students, at Irbid First Educational Directorate schools from teachers' standpoint?

To answer this question, the relationship between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their tasks and the practice degree of positive behaviors among students was tested by conducting the Pearson test to examine the linear correlation between variables, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Sorrelation coefficients between the aspects of school principals' performance and students' behaviors

Tasks	Positive Behaviors	Administrative Tasks	Technical Tasks	Overall Tasks
Student behaviors toward school		**0.966	**0.934	**0.961
Student behaviors toward classmates		**0.950	**0.924	**0.947
Positive Behavior as a whole		**0.978	**0.948	**0.974

It notices from Table 7, the existence of a statistically significant direct correlation at level ($\alpha=0.05$) between each of student's behavior toward school and student behavior toward classmates and the positive behavior among students as a whole, and the practice of high school principals toward their tasks where the values of Pearson correlation were positive and amounted to (0.96, 0.94, 0.97), which indicate a direct relationship as shown from the statistical significance. It also shows the existance of positive direct correlation between the attitudes or behaviors and each of the administrative tasks and the technical tasks.

4.7. Discuss the results of third question, which entitle:

Is there any statistical significance correlation at level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their administrative and technical tasks and the practice degree of positive behaviors among students, at Irbid First Educational Directorate schools from teachers' standpoint?

The results of this question showed the existence of a statistically significance correlation at level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the practice degree of secondary school principals toward their tasks and the practice degree of positive behaviors among students in at Irbid First Educational Directorate schools, from the standpoint of teachers where the Pearson correlation coefficient were indicating positive values, which indicate a direct relationship and this result means that practice of school principals to their assigned tasks result in the practice of positive behaviors by the students, and this could mean there is a significant correlation between the behavior of principal and positive behavior of students. The positive learning and positive behavior theory [23] explained the way to learn social behavior, and found that most types of social behavior would be learn from observing and watching others, and demonstrate that some responses would be learn through watching and observing the behavior of others, especially there are certain types of behavior that do not comprehend without the social practices, where learning by example and learning by modeling method must be used in such cases, and as mentioned by Pandora when someone get exposed to the model the following will occur [24, 25].

- a. Obtain a new style of response that wasn't identified previously by the person observed.
- b. Facilitate or restrain the related response patterns that weren't previously recognized.
- c. Retrieve responses from the observer's mind similar to the model responses.

School principal consider the cornerstone of the school, where all elements of the teaching and learning process like teachers, students, parents, and curriculum will be influence by the principal, and the condition of students may rehabilitate by the reform of the principal and it may be vice versa too. The result can be attributed to the influence authorities of school administration on all school staff, which reflected on their behaviors and in turn reflected on the students' behaviors. It may also be attributed to the nature of existing relations between teachers and the school management, and as long as this positive relationship exist it will facilitate the tasks of principals and increase their positive impact on everyone, which drive students to demonstrate the positive behaviors and reflect good manners that make everyone satisfied.

5. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that, when the principals do not perform their duties properly, do not collect data about students accurately, lack of dealing with students with humanity, do not delegate tasks on teachers based on their competencies, and do not care about following the work of school committees, but instead there is a clear failure in all administrative and technical tasks of school principals, which reflected badly on all inputs and outputs of education process, not achieving the planned educational objectives, and the threat of arriving to undesirable results in the educational system. In order to obtain a good outcom, the principals should take care in all required, which could help teachers to do their duties, and run after all the problems and find the solutions. From the related studies and literature, the researchers found that there is a relationship of principals behavior and teacher behavior which reflect on student's behavior.

We recommend to the principals: 1) strengthen monitoring and supervision of school principals to carry out their duties properly; 2) pay attention to activate the council of local community in solving student problems; 3) developing and preparing various activities that serve the school curriculum, and 4) search for practical, professional and realistic solutions to the problems facing teachers in the school. Further researchers should conduct more studies on the behavior of students in schools and linking them with other variables such as educational attainment or the family's social status.

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